

Immature stages of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae, HesperIIDinae, HesperIIDini, Moncina): biology, morphology and behaviour

Arthur Morais de Medeiros¹, Adalberto Dantas de Medeiros², Solange Maria Kerpel³

(1) [Corresponding author] Laboratório de Ecologia e Interações de Insetos da Caatinga, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Centro de Saúde e Tecnologia Rural, Unidade Acadêmica de Ciências Biológicas. Av. Universitária, Santa Cecília, 58708–110 Patos, Paraíba, Brazil, arthurmoraismedeiros@gmail.com

(2) Laboratório em Estudos em Lepidoptera Neotropical, Departamento de Zoologia, Universidade Federal do Paraná, P.O. Box 19.020, 81.531–980 Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil, adalberto.dantasufpr@gmail.com

(3) Laboratório de Ecologia e Interações de Insetos da Caatinga, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Centro de Saúde e Tecnologia Rural, Unidade Acadêmica de Ciências Biológicas. Av. Universitária, Santa Cecília, 58708–110 Patos, Paraíba, Brazil, solakerpel@gmail.com

Abstract: The biology, morphology, and behaviour of the immature stages of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) are described from eggs and larvae collected in two areas in the Caatinga biome, Northeast region of Brazil. The larvae of *C. saturnus* go through five larval instars with a development time ranging between 28 and 33 days. The eggs are dome-shaped and are laid singly on the adaxial region of the leaves of the host plant, *Panicum trichoides* Sw. (Poaceae). The larvae are green, with head coloration varying among the different instars, and they construct three types of shelters: a one-cut shelter (Greeney's type 4), built by the first instar larva; a two-cut shelter (Greeney's type 5), built by the second instar larva; and no-cut shelters (Greeney's type 1), built by the larvae of the remaining instars. Considering the lack of information about the morphology and behaviour of the larvae of *Callimormus* species, our study represents an important step towards understanding the natural history of species in this genus, contributing essentially to its taxonomy, the establishment of phylogenetic relationships, and the conservation of skippers in general.

Keywords: Caatinga biome, natural history, *Panicum trichoides*, skipper

Introduction

Butterflies and moths are included in Lepidoptera, one of the four largest insect orders in species diversity (Nieukerken et al., 2011). Due to their common presence and abundance in nearly all terrestrial environments, and their remarkable diversity in wing coloration patterns, butterflies are among the most extensively studied groups by professional and amateur researchers (Devries, 1987; Warren et al., 2008). As a result, butterflies have been widely employed as models in genetic, evolutionary, and ecological studies (Hill et al., 2021; Ficarrota et al., 2022; Melo et al., 2023).

Despite recent advances in the understanding of butterfly systematics and taxonomy (Espeland et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022, 2023; Kawahara et al., 2023), the knowledge of their immature stages remains limited, especially for families with a high diversity of cryptic, small, and inconspicuously coloured species, such as HesperIIDae. Even the most abundant, widely distributed, and frequently recorded skippers lack detailed information on their morphology, biology, and behaviour (Mielke, 2024a). Generally, the scant available information relates to a specific developmental stage or the identification of host plants, rendering these data sources inadequate for

use in phylogenetic and comparative morphology studies (Moss, 1949; Becalloni et al., 2008; Warren et al., 2009; Cock, 2011). This situation is even more noticeable for Neotropical skippers.

Among the Neotropical HesperIIDae genera with little known natural history, *Callimormus* Scudder, 1872 (HesperIIDae, HesperIIDinae, HesperIIDini, Moncina) stands out. This genus currently comprises ten species and four subspecies (Zhang et al., 2023; Mielke, 2024b). These species occur from Mexico to Bolivia, Paraguay, northern Argentina and Uruguay, at altitudes ranging from sea level to 2,600 metres (Medeiros et al., 2019; Gallardo, 2023; Gualberto et al., 2024). Despite the relatively high frequency of *Callimormus* in inventories (Mielke & Casagrande, 1991; Ruszczyk & Silva, 1997; Zacca & Bravo, 2012; Kerpel et al., 2014; Dantas et al., 2021; Ferreira-Junior, 2021; Medeiros et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2023; Gualberto et al., 2024), host plants have been recorded for six of its species only, including *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869),

which is the subject of the present research (Pastrana et al., 2004; Beccaloni et al., 2008; Warren et al., 2009; Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009; Cock, 2011). However, a complete description of the morphology and behaviour of its entire developmental stages have not been undertaken yet.

Thus, this study aims to describe the biology, morphology, and behaviour of the immature stages of *C. saturnus*, aiming to contribute to the understanding of its natural history and provide data for phylogenetic studies of Neotropical skippers.

Methods

Study area

The immature stages of *C. saturnus* were collected at Inselberg Serrote da Cruz (ISC) (7°2'47.17" S, 37°15'30.48" W, 280 m a.s.l.) (for the definition of Inselberg, see Porembski & Barthlott, 2000 and

Figs 1–3. Collection sites of immatures of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869). 1. Map of Brazil with emphasis on the Northeast region (grey) and the state of Paraíba (green). 2. Map of Paraíba with emphasis on the municipality of Patos. 3. Map of the municipality of Patos with the Inselbergs Serrote da Cruz (ISC) and Condomínio Residencial Villas do Lago (CRVL) highlighted.

Figs 4–7. *Panicum trichoides* Sw. (Poaceae), the host plant of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869) in the collection environments. 6. Inselberg Serrote da Cruz (ISC). 7. Condomínio Residencial Villas do Lago (CRVL).

Velloso et al., 2002) and at Condomínio Residencial Villas do Lago (CRVL) (7°2'23" S, 37°16'57" W, 240 m a.s.l.). ISC and CRVL respectively are in the rural and urban landscapes of Patos municipality, state of Paraíba, Brazil, both are situated in a Caatinga biome area highly impacted by anthropogenic activities (Figs 1–3). The vegetation is classified as a seasonally dry tropical forest (Silva et al., 2017), the climate is classified as Bsh, hot and dry according to the Köppen classification, and the average annual rainfall is 700 mm (Beltrão et al., 2005), with most rainfall occurring between January and July.

Collection and rearing of immatures

Larvae and eggs of *C. saturnus* were collected on *Panicum trichoides* Sw. (Poaceae) leaves from October 2022 to September 2023 (Figs 4–7). The search for immatures occurred during four consecutive hours every 15 days between October and December 2022, and one day per week after the

first rains (January to May 2023). From June to August 2023, collections were daily conducted or every two days. A specimen of the host plant was collected and sent for identification by an expert (see Acknowledgments section), and the voucher (CSTR 8040) was deposited at the Herbarium CSTR Rita Baltazar of the Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Patos, Paraíba, Brazil.

The leaves containing immatures were detached and placed in closed, transparent plastic containers of 500 ml, which were then transported to the laboratory. To prevent dehydration, the petiole of the leaves was wrapped in moistened cotton. Simultaneously, the bottom of the containers was covered with absorbent paper to avoid excessive humidity. Rearing was conducted at room temperature (approximately 27–30°C).

Immatures were monitored daily to assess for egg hatching, larval moulting, pupation, and adult emergence. Dates of occurrences and observations regarding shelter construction and other behavioural aspects were recorded. In the event of moulting, the head capsule was collected and stored in labelled Eppendorf

tubes for subsequent measurement, illustration, and morphological description. Host plant leaves were replaced, and containers were cleaned daily after observations. Emerged adults were mounted, labelled, and deposited in the Laboratório de Ecologia e Interações de Insetos da Caatinga Collection (CLEIIC), Centro de Saúde e Tecnologia Rural, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Patos, Paraíba, Brazil.

Morphological studies

The morphological analysis and measurements of the immatures were conducted using a stereomicroscope equipped with an attached micrometric scale. Photographs of the head capsules were captured using a digital camera supported by Leica LAS 3D view and LAS montage version 4.7 software as the focus stacking system. The remaining photographs were taken with a digital camera. The measurement of the head capsules considered the widest portion of the head.

Colour descriptions of the immatures were made from live specimens to prevent alteration in their characteristics. Larvae were killed in hot water, fixed in Dietrich's solution for 24 hours, and subsequently preserved in 70% alcohol (Stehr, 1987). Three specimens (first, fourth, and fifth larval instars) were preserved and deposited in CLEIIC for future studies. Morphological terminology for the immatures was based on Stehr (1987), and shelter nomenclature followed Greeney (2009).

Results

A total of 17 immatures of *C. saturnus* (3 eggs and 14 larvae) were collected on *P. trichoides* leaves. Of the 14 larvae, 12 were in the first instar, one in the second instar, and one in the third instar. No pupae were found. Only one larva was collected at the first study site (ISC); the remaining individuals were collected at the second area (CRVL). Of the *C. saturnus* larvae reared in the laboratory, 12 reached adulthood, two died from unknown causes, and the remaining individuals were killed and preserved.

The larvae of *C. saturnus* go through five larval instars, with the development ranging from 28 to 33 days. However, this duration may be a bit longer, as none of the eggs was collected immediately after oviposition.

Morphological description of immature stages

Egg (Figs 8–9): dome-shaped, translucent white; micropylar area slightly invaginated; chorion smooth but with micro sculpturing resembling webs, not seen without magnification. Eggs are consistently found on the abaxial surface of the leaf.

First instar (Figs 10–11, 20): head shiny black, apparently smooth, trapezoidal, with a slightly excavated epicranial notch (Fig. 20); primary setae small and sparse. Prothorax with black rectangular dorsal plate; spiracles not darkened. Body translucent cream after hatching, becoming greenish after feeding; segments slightly laterally projected; dorsal area with central darkened longitudinal stripe; spiracles of abdominal segment VIII not darkened. Head capsule width: 0.38–0.46 mm (n=8) Development time: 2–3 days (n=10).

Second instar (Figs 12–13, 21): head shiny black, slightly rough, trapezoidal (Fig. 21); numerous and elongated secondary setae. Prothorax similar to that of the first instar. Body light green laterally, darker dorsally from the fourth segment, with slight opacity in the last two segments; dorsal area with central darkened longitudinal stripe; spiracles of the abdominal segment VIII not darkened. Head capsule width: 0.52–0.65 mm (n=14). Development time: 2–4 days (n=10).

Third instar (Figs 14–15, 22): head shiny black and rough, trapezoidal (Fig. 22); setae similar to those in the second instar, but longer. Prothorax with black rectangular dorsal plate; spiracles slightly darkened. Body greenish, with numerous dark green spots at the base of the setae; dorsal region with three dark green longitudinal stripes, the central stripe being more prominent; spiracles of the abdominal segment VIII slightly darkened. Head capsule width: 0.77–0.88 mm (n=13). Development time: 2–6 days (n=14).

Fourth instar (Figs 16–17, 23): head dark brownish black, trapezoidal, with the following cream-coloured spot pattern: two longitudinal stripes parallel to the epicranial suture, from the vertex to the ecdysial line; two irregular lateral spots, one over the stemmata semicircle and another between the stemmata and the frontoclypeus; two pairs of frontal spots: one on the upper portion of the adfrontal area and another in the central region of the frons (Fig. 23). Prothorax with a rectangular plate similar to that of the third instar, but with concave anterior and posterior margins; spiracles not darkened. Body as in the third instar, differing by the more prominent abdominal

Figs 8–19. Immature stages of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869). 8–9. Egg in dorsal view on the leaf. 10–19. Larva in dorsal (left) and lateral views (right). 10–11. First instar. 12–13. Second instar. 14–15. Third instar. 16–17. Fourth instar. 18–19. Fifth instar. Scale 2 mm.

stripes and the spiracles of the abdominal segment VIII darkened. Head capsule width: 1.08–1.21 mm (n=14). Development time: 2–5 days (n=14).

Fifth instar (Figs 18–19, 24): head with a spot pattern similar to that of the fourth instar, differing in

the larger extent of the cream spots (Fig. 24). Prothorax with dorsal plate reduced to two narrow lateral stripes; spiracles similar to those of the fourth instar. Body as in the fourth instar, differing in the non-darkened spiracles of the abdominal segment

Figs 20–24. Head capsules of the five larval instars of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869). 20. First instar. 21. Second instar. 22. Third instar. 23. Fourth instar. 24. Fifth instar. Scale 0,5 mm.

VIII. The head capsule width was not recorded due to the rupture of the ecdysial line before pupation. Development time: 7–10 days (n=13).

Pupa (Figs 25–30): light green, translucent in the thoracic region, with scattered white setae, more abundant on the head and abdomen. Body tapered to-

wards the cremaster, with a light coating of whitish wax. Proboscis not reaching the cremaster, with the distal half not fused to the body and slightly darker in colour. Eyes light green, turning reddish before adult emergence (Figs 29–30). Development time: 7–8 days (n=11).

Figs 25–33. Pupa and adults of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869). 25–30. Pupa. 25. Dorsal view. 26. Lateral view. 27. Ventral view. 28. Frontal view of the head. 29–30. Pupa with reddish eyes before adult emergence in lateral and frontal views. Scale 2 mm. 31–33. Adult male. 31. Dorsal view. 32. Ventral view. Scale 1 cm. 33. Lateral view resting on vegetation.

Figs 34–39. Shelters constructed by the larvae of *Callimormus saturnus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1869). 34–35. One-cut shelters (type 4) built by the first instar larva (red arrows indicate silk threads used in shelter construction). 36. Two-cut shelter (type 5) built by second instar larva. 37–38. No-cut shelters (type 1) constructed by larvae of later instars (red arrows indicate silk threads used in shelter construction). 39. Shelter built by the fifth instar larva before pupation.

Biology and behaviour of the immature stages

Eggs of *C. saturnus* were found on the adaxial surface of the leaves (Figs 4–7). After hatching, the first instar larvae consume the chorion and usually move to the apex or margin of the leaf, where they start constructing their first shelter (Figs 34–35). Feeding occurs at night, starting at 6 pm. By this time the larvae leave the shelter, remaining partially or fully exposed. First and second instar larvae eat the host plant leaf from the lateral margins or by making holes in the limbus, near the shelter. In later instars, the larvae consume the entire leaf limbus, including the portion used for shelter construction. After consuming the shelter, the larvae seek new leaves and restart the shelter construction process. In all instars, *C. saturnus* larvae eject their excrement outside the shelter.

Callimormus saturnus larvae construct three shelter types: 1, 4, and 5, following Greeney's classification (Greeney, 2009). The first instar larvae build one-cut shelters (type 4) by cutting the leaf from its margin towards the central vein. After cutting it, the first instar larvae roll the cut portion toward the adaxial surface of the leaf and secure it with silk, forming a tubular structure with openings at both ends (Figs 34–35). Second instar larvae construct a double-cut shel-

ter (type 5), making two cuts along the leaf margins. The portion of the leaf between these cuts is rolled towards the central vein and fixed with silk.

From the third instar onwards, *C. saturnus* larvae construct no-cut shelters (type 1) by folding and, subsequently, joining or bringing together the leaf margins using silk threads (Figs 36–38). At the end of the fifth instar, a no-cut shelter is also built to protect the pupa (Fig. 39).

Discussion

Callimormus saturnus (Figs 31–33) is commonly represented in surveys, occurring in both natural and human-modified environments of moist forests and seasonally dry forests (Mielke & Casagrande, 1991; Ruszczyk & Silva, 1997; Zacca & Bravo, 2012; Kerpel et al., 2014; Dantas et al., 2021; Ferreira-Junior, 2021; Medeiros et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2023; Gualberto et al., 2024). This species occurs throughout the year in the Caatinga biome, flying near the ground in typically humid and shaded environments (Nobre & Schlindwein, 2016). We had previously recorded this species at ISC on different occasions, but during the current research, only one adult and a single larva were

observed at this site. The reduction in abundance of the species at ISC may have been due to the late arrival of rains which delayed the germination of its host plant, as well as deforestation and wildfires observed during the collections. This fact highlights the importance of preserving habitats on Inselbergs to maintain the fauna and flora of a region.

Panicum trichoides is a common herbaceous species in tropical regions worldwide and is distributed across almost all Brazilian biomes, except for the Pampa (Rodrigues, 2015). In the Caatinga, it primarily grows during the rainy season and may completely disappear during dry months. It is found in various microhabitats including plain terrain, rocky areas, and riparian forests (Andrade et al., 2007). Numerous records exist documenting this plant as a host plant of skippers, and also moths from the families Noctuidae and Pyralidae (Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009). In the Caatinga, the plant also serves as food for other hesperiids such as *Vehilius jabre* Medeiros, Souza & Kerpel, 2023 (Souza et al., 2023) and *Lerodea erythrostictus* (Prittwitz, 1868) (authors' observation). Therefore, conservation of the habitats where *P. trichoides* is found is critical, ensuring the preservation of both the plant and the fauna reliant upon it.

In general, species of *Callimormus* are oligophagous, with larvae feeding on various species of Poaceae. For example, *C. saturnus* uses, in addition to *P. trichoides*, species of the genera *Acroceras* Staph, *Ischaemum* L., *Panicum* L., *Paspalum* L., *Rottboellia* L.f., and *Zea* L. as host plants (Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009). Oligophagy has also been observed in *Callimormus corades* (C. Felder, 1862) and *C. juvenis* Scudder, 1872 (Remillet, 1998; Beccaloni et al., 2008; Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009; Cock, 2011). Despite the presence of *Paspalum* species in the study area, *C. saturnus* larvae were only found on *P. trichoides*. Conversely, Janzen & Hallwachs (2009) recorded five larvae of this skipper on *Paspalum* and only three on *Panicum* in a moist forest area in Mexico. Thus, the absence of *C. saturnus* on *Paspalum* may indicate a potential dietary preference for *Panicum* species in the Caatinga. However, such preference has not been scientifically tested yet.

Five larval instars were recorded for *C. saturnus*. Although this number varies among different Hesperidae subfamilies (Silva et al., 2021), five seems to be the most common number of instars for Hesperinae (Greeney & Warren, 2009; Freitas, 2018; Freitas, 2020; Souza et al., 2023). However, it is

known that the number of instars in a species may vary depending on factors directly affecting development, such as the type of food consumed (Silva & Carvalho, 2004; Kerpel et al., 2006).

As above mentioned, larvae of *C. saturnus* construct three types of larval shelters. Larval shelters occur in about 18 families of Lepidoptera (Bächtold et al., 2012) and are generally associated with defence against natural enemies (Eubanks et al., 1997; Greeney et al., 2012). Although shelters constructed by Hesperidae larvae have long been documented, they have only been systematically studied in recent decades, with the proposal of a classification system for shelters built by Pyrginae larvae (Weiss, 2003; Greeney, 2009). However, the use of these data as a source of phylogenetic information has not been explored yet, mainly because most species in the family lack information on the biology and behaviour of their immature stages.

As observed in other species of Hesperidae, larvae of *C. saturnus* eject their excrements outside the shelter (Weiss, 2006; Lepsqueur et al., 2017; Souza et al., 2023). This strategy maximises larval survival by preventing contact with pathogens such as bacteria, fungi, and protozoa, which can proliferate in faeces leading to pathologies and death (Hajek & Leger, 1994). Furthermore, ejecting excrement away from the larva's location eliminates olfactory cues of its presence to potential predators and parasitoids (Weiss et al., 2003; Weiss, 2003, 2006).

Although species of *Callimormus* are widely distributed throughout the Neotropical region, little information is available regarding the morphology and coloration patterns of the larvae within the genus. The only available illustration is from the final instar larva of *C. juvenis* (Janzen & Hallwachs, 2009). Here, for the first time, we provide a complete description of the post embryonic development of a species in this genus, covering all immature stages. Therefore, our study represents a significant step towards understanding the natural history of Neotropical skippers, as it contributes fundamentally to the taxonomy, phylogenetic relationships, and conservation efforts within the group.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our sincere thanks to the members of the Laboratório de Ecologia e Interações

dos Insetos da Caatinga (LEIIC) for their assistance in collecting the immature specimens. Professor Dr Jefferson Maciel for the host plant identification. Dr Maria de Fátima de Araújo for incorporating the host plant specimen into the Herbarium CSTR Rita Baltazar at the Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Patos, Paraíba, Brazil. Universidade Federal de Campina Grande for the logistical support provided during the collections. Finally, we thank Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico – Brazil (CNPq) for granting the first author the opportunity to participate in the Voluntary Scientific Initiation Program and the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) for the research fellowship to ADM (88887.941144/2024-00).

References

- Andrade J.R., Santos J.M.F.F., Lima E.N., Silva K.A., Lopes C.G.R., Araújo E.L. 2007 Estudo populacional de *Panicum trichoides* Swart. (Poaceae) em uma área de Caatinga em Caruaru, Pernambuco. *Revista Brasileira de Biociências* 5 (1): 858–860.
- Bächtold A., Del-Claro K., Kaminski L.A., Freitas A.V.L., Oliveira P.S. 2012 Natural history of an ant-plant-butterfly interaction in a Neotropical savanna. *Journal of Natural History* 46 (15–16): 943–954.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2011.651649>
- Beccaloni G.W., Vilorio A.L., Hall S.K., Robinson G. 2008 Catalogue of the hostplants of the Neotropical butterflies. *Catálogo de las plantas huésped de las mariposas neotropicales. Monografías del Tercer Milenio* 8: 1–536.
- Beltrão B.A., Morais F., Mascarenhas J.C., Miranda J.L.F., Junior L.C.S., Mendes V.A. 2005 Diagnóstico do município de Patos, estado da Paraíba. CPRM/PRODEEM, Recife, 26 pp.
- Cock M.J. 2011 The Skipper Butterflies (Hesperiidae) of Trinidad Part 18, Hesperinae, Moncini: Eight Genera of Relatively Distinctive Species: *Callimormus*, *Eutocus*, *Artines*, *Flaccilla*, *Phanes*, *Monca*, *Vehilius* and *Parphorus*. *Living World* 2011: 14–36.
- Dantas C., Zacca T., Bravo F. 2021 Checklist of butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) of an urban area of Caatinga-Atlantic Forest ecotone in Bahia, Brazil. *EntomoBrasilis* 14: e959.
<https://doi.org/10.12741/ebrasilis.v14.e959>
- Devries P.J. 1987 The Butterflies of Costa Rica and Their Natural History. Vol I: Papilionidae, Pieridae, Nymphalidae. Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey, 327 pp.
- Espeland M., Breinholt J.W., Willmott K.R., Warren A.D., Vila-Ujaldón R., Toussaint E.F.A., Maunsell S.C., Aduse-Poku K., Talavera-Mor G., Eastwood R., Jarzyna M.A., Guralnick R.P., Lohman Jr D.J., Pierce N.E., Kawahara A.Y. 2018 A comprehensive and dated phylogenomic analysis of butterflies. *Current Biology* 28 (5): 770–778.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.01.061>
- Eubanks M.D., Nesci K.A., Petersen M.K., Liu Z., Sanchez H.B. 1997 The exploitation of an ant-defended host plant by a shelter-building herbivore. *Oecologia* 109: 454–460.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s004420050105>
- Ferreira-Junior A. 2021 Butterflies diversity from a remnant of semiurban Caatinga, Septentrional Sertaneja Depression Ecoregion, Patos, Paraíba, Brazil (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). *SHILAP Revista de Lepidopterología* 49 (194): 327–349.
<https://doi.org/10.57065/shilap.303>
- Freitas A.V.L. 2018 Immature stages of the Neotropical skipper *Lychnuchoides ozias ozias* (Hewitson, 1878) (Lepidoptera: Hesperidae). *Tropical Lepidoptera Research* 28 (1): 25–28.
- Freitas A.V.L. 2020 Immature stages of the Neotropical skipper *Saliana longirostris* (Sepp, [1840]) (Lepidoptera: Hesperidae). *Tropical Lepidoptera Research* 30 (2): 81–85.
- Gallardo R.J. 2023 Inventory of butterflies of Emerald Valley Nature Reserve, Honduras (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). *Tropical Lepidoptera Research* 33 (1): 1–22.
- Greeney H.F., Warren A.D. 2009 The immature stages and shelter building behavior of *Falga jeconia ombra* Evans, 1955 in eastern Ecuador (Lepidoptera: Hesperidae: Hesperinae). *Journal of Insect Science* 9 (33): 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1673/031.009.3301>
- Greeney H.F. 2009 A revised classification scheme for larval hesperiid shelters, with comments on shelter diversity in the Pyrginae. *Journal of Research on the Lepidoptera* 41 (2002): 53–59.

- Greeney H.F., Dyer L.A., Smilanich A.M. 2012 Feeding by lepidopteran larvae is dangerous: a review of caterpillars' chemical, physiological, morphological, and behavioral defenses against natural enemies. *Invertebrate Survival Journal* 9 (1): 7–34.
- Gualberto E.P., Medeiros A.D., Kerpel S.M. 2024 Butterflies of two atlantic forest conservation units from Paraíba state, northeast of Brazil. *EntomoBrasilis* 17 (1068): 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.12741/ebrasilis.v17.e1068>
- Hajek A.E., St. Leger R.J. 1994 Interactions between fungal pathogens and insect hosts. *Annual Review of Entomology* 39 (1): 293–322.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.en.39.010194.001453>
- Hill G.M., Kawahara A.Y., Daniels J.C., Bateman C.C., Scheffers B.R. 2021 Climate change effects on animal ecology: butterflies and moths as a case study. *Biological Reviews* 96 (5): 2113–2126.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12746>
- Janzen D.H., Hallwachs W. 2009 Dynamic database for an inventory of the macrocaterpillar fauna, and its food plants and parasitoids, of Area de Conservacion Guanacaste (ACG), northwestern Costa Rica (nn-SRNP-nnnnn voucher codes). <http://janzen.sas.upenn.edu> (accessed 21 June 2024).
- Kawahara A.Y., Storer C., Carvalho A.P.S., Plotkin D.M., Condamine F.L., Braga M.P., Ellis E.A., St Laurent R.A., Li X., Barve V., Cai L., Earl C., Frandsen P.B., Owens H.L., Valencia-Montoya W.A., Aduse-Poku K., Toussaint E.F.A., Dexter K.M., Doleck T., Markee A., Messcher R., Nguyen Y., Badon J.A.T., Benítez H.A., Braby M.F., Buenavente P.A.C., Chan W., Collins S.C., Childers R.A.R., Dankowicz E., Eastwood R., Fric Z.F., Gott R.J., Hall J.P.W., Hallwachs W., Hardy N.B., Sipe R.L.H., Heath A., Hinolan J.D., Homziak N.T., Hsu Y., Inayoshi Y., Ithiong M.G.A., Janzen D.H., Kitching I.J., Kunte K., Lamas G., Landis M.J., Larsen E.A., Larsen T.B., Leong J.V., Lukhtanov V., Maier C.A., Martinez J.I., Martins D.J., Maruyama K., Maunsell S.C., Mega Nicolás O., Monastyrskii A., Morais A.B.B., Müller C.J., Naive M.A.K., Nielsen G., Padrón P.S., Peggie D., Romanowski H.P., Sáfían S., Saito M., Schröder S., Shirey V., Soltis D., Soltis P., Sourakov A., Talavera G., Vila R., Vlasanek P., Wang H., Warren A.D., Willmott K.R., Yago M., Jetz W., Jarzyna M.A., Breinholt J.W., Espeland M., Ries L., Guralnick R.P., Pierce N.E., Lohman D.J. 2023 A global phylogeny of butterflies reveals their evolutionary history, ancestral hosts, and biogeographic origins. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7 (6): 903–913.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02041-9>
- Kerpel S.M., Soprano E., Moreira G.R. 2006 Effect of nitrogen on *Passiflora suberosa* L. (Passifloraceae) and consequences for larval performance and oviposition in *Heliconius erato phyllis* (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae). *Neotropical Entomology* 35 (2): 192–200.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/S1519-566X2006000200006>
- Kerpel S.M., Zacca T., Nobre C.E.B., Ferreira-Junior A., Araújo M.X., Fonseca A. 2014 Borboletas do Semiárido, conhecimento atual e contribuições do PPBio. *Artrópodes do Semi-Árido: biodiversidade e conservação*. In: Bravo F., Calor A.R. (eds) *Artrópodes do Semiárido: biodiversidade e conservação*. Feira de Santana, Printmídia, 245–275.
- Lepesqueur C., Neis M., Silva N.A., Pereira T., Rodrigues H.P.A., Trindade T., Diniz I.R. 2017 *Elbella luteizona* (Mabille, 1877) (Lepidoptera, Hesperidae: Pyrginae) in Brazilian Cerrado: larval morphology, diet, and shelter architecture. *Revista Brasileira de Entomologia* 61: 282–289.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbe.2017.08.004>
- Li W., Cong Q., Shen J., Zhang J., Hallwachs W., Janzen D.H., Grishin N.V. 2019 Genomes of skipper butterflies reveal extensive convergence of wing patterns. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 116 (13): 6232–6237.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.182130411>
- Medeiros A.D., Dolibaina D.R., Carneiro E., Mielke O.H.H., Casagrande M.M. 2019 Taxonomic revision of *Artines* Godman, 1901 (Hesperidae: Hesperinae: Moncini) with the description of nine new species. *Zootaxa* 4614 (1): 1–49.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4614.1.1>
- Medeiros A.D., Gualberto E.P., Rodrigues R.P., Kerpel S.M. 2021 Butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) of the Restinga de Cabedelo National Forest, Paraíba State, Brazil. *EntomoBrasilis* 14: e970.
<https://doi.org/10.12741/ebrasilis.v14.e970>

- Melo D.H.A., Freitas A.V.L., Tabarelli M., Filgueiras B.K.C., Leal I.R. 2023 Aridity and chronic anthropogenic disturbance as organizing forces of fruit-feeding butterfly assemblages in a Caatinga dry forest. *Biotropica* 55 (1): 173–184.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/btp.13173>
- Mielke O.H.H., Casagrande M.M. 1991 Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea e Hesperioidea coletados na Ilha de Maracá, Alto Alegre, Roraima, parte do projeto Maracá, com uma lista complementar de Hesperiidae de Roraima. *Acta Amazonica* 21: 175–210.
- Mielke O.H.H. 2024a Checklist of the American Hesperiidae. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/17A17rT-Ba12N8EX66IoNTSkTSLjIc9BE/view> (accessed 21 June 2024).
- Mielke O.H.H. 2024b Catalogue of the American Hesperiidae, Volume 7. <https://sites.google.com/site/lablepneo/publica%C3%A7%C3%B5es/livros> (accessed 21 June 2024).
- Montero-Abril F., Ortiz-Pérez M., Le Crom J.F. 2021 Diversidad de mariposas diurnas (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) en la parte media y baja del Río Mocoa, Putumayo, Colombia. *Conservación Colombiana* 27: 28–59.
<https://doi.org/10.54588/cc2021v27n01a03>
- Moss A.M. 1949 Biological notes on some “Hesperiidae” of Pará and the Amazon (Lep. Rhop.). *Acta Zoologica Lilloana* 7: 27–79.
- Ficarrota V., Hanly J.J., Loh L.S., Francescutti C.M., Ren A., Tunström K., Wheat C.W., Porter A.H., Counterman B.A., Arnaud Martin A. 2022 A genetic switch for male UV iridescence in an incipient species pair of sulphur butterflies. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 119 (3): e2109255118.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2109255118>
- Nieukerken E.J., Kaila L., Kitching I.J., Kristensen N.P., Lees D.C., Minet J., Mitter C., Mutanen M., Regier J.C., Simonsen T.J., Wahlberg N., Yen S.H., Zahiri R., Adamski D., Baixeras-Almela J., Bartsch D., Bengtsson B.Å., Brown J.W., Bucheli S.R., Davis D.R., Prins J., Prins W., Epstein M.E., Gentili-Poole P., Gielis C., Hättenschwiler P., Hausmann A., Holloway J.D., Kallies A., Karsholt O., Kawahara A.Y., Koster S., Kozlov M.V., Lafontaine J.D., Lamas G., Landry J.F., Lee S., Nuss M., Park K.T., Penz C.M., Rota J., Schintlmeister A., Schmidt B.C., Sohn J.C., Solís M.A., Tarmann G.M., Warren A.D., Weller S.J., Yakovlev R.V., Zolotuhin V.V., Zwick A. 2011 Order Lepidoptera, pp. 212–221. In: Zhang Z.-Q. An outline of higher-level classification and survey of taxonomic richness. *Zootaxa* 3148 (1): 1–237.
- Nobre C.E.B., Schlindwein C. 2016 Borboletas no Vale do Catimbau: guia de espécies e flores visitadas. Verbes Editora, Brasília, 280 pp.
- Pastrana J.A., Di Iorio O.R., Navarro F.R., Chalup A.E., Villagrán M.E. 2004 Lepidoptera. In: Cordo H.A., Logarzo G.A., Braun K., Di Iorio O.R. (eds) Catálogo de insectos fitófagos de la Argentina y sus plantas asociadas. Buenos Aires, Sociedad Entomológica Argentina, xvii + 720 pp.
- Porembski S., Barthlott W. 2000 Granitic and gneissic outcrops (inselbergs) as centers of diversity for desiccation-tolerant vascular plants. *Plant Ecology* 151: 19–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026565817218>
- Remillet M. 1988 Catalogue des insectes ravageurs des cultures en Guyane Française. ORSDOM, Paris, 235 pp.
- Rodrigues R.S. 2015 *Panicum* in Lista de Espécies da Flora do Brasil. Jardim Botânico do Rio de Janeiro. <http://floradobrasil2015.jbrj.gov.br/jabot/floradobrasil/FB20450> (accessed 12 June 2024).
- Ruszczyk A., Silva C.F. 1997 As borboletas selecionam microhabitats nas paredes dos edificios. *Paisagismo e Planejamento Urbano* 38 (1–2): 119–127.
- Santos L.N.D., Kerpel S.M., Medeiros A.D., Brito M.R.M.D. 2023 Borboletas no Nordeste: as borboletas em áreas protegidas de florestas nordestinas. EDUFCEG, Campina Grande, 98 pp.
- Silva A.M., Medeiros A.D., Kerpel S.M. 2021 Immature stages of *Nisoniades macarius* (Hesperiidae: Pyrginae: Carcharodini): biology, morphology and behavior. *Iheringia. Série Zoologia* 111: 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-4766e2021027>
- Silva E.J., Carvalho A.G. 2004 Influencia de *Clitoria fairchildiana*, *Desmodium incanum* e *Galactia striata* (Leguminosae) na biologia de *Urbanus acawoios* (Lepidoptera: Hesperiidae). *Quebracho-Revista de Ciencias Forestales* (11): 33–41.
- Silva J.M.C., Barbosa L.C.F., Leal I.R., Tabarelli M. 2017 The Caatinga: Understanding the Challenges. In: Silva J.M.C., Leal I.R., Tabarelli M. (eds) Caatinga: The largest tropical dry forest

- region in South America. Springer International Publishing 1: 3–19.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68339-3_1
- Souza J.A., Medeiros A.D., Dolibaina D.R., Kerpel S.M. 2023 A new species of *Vehilius* Godman, 1900 (Lepidoptera, HesperIIDae, HesperIIDae) endemic to the Caatinga, northeastern Brazil: taxonomy, biology and behavior. *Zootaxa* 5360 (2): 239–254.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5360.2.4>
- Stehr F.W. 1987 Immature insects. Kendall/Hunt Publishing, Dubuque, 770 pp.
- Velloso A.L., Sampaio E.V.S.B., Pareyn F.G.C. 2002 Ecorregiões propostas para o bioma Caatinga. Associação Plantas do Nordeste. Instituto de Conservação Ambiental The Nature Conservancy do Brasil, Recife, 76 pp.
- Warren A.D., Ogawa J.R., Brower A.V.Z. 2008 Phylogenetic relationships of subfamilies and circumscription of tribes in the family HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea). *Cladistics* 24 (5): 642–676.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-0031.2008.00218.x>
- Warren A.D., Ogawa J.R., Brower A.V.Z. 2009 Revised classification of the family HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea) based on combined molecular and morphological data. *Systematic Entomology* 34 (3): 467–523.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.2008.00463.x>
- Weiss M.R. 2003 Good housekeeping: why do shelter-dwelling caterpillars fling their frass? *Ecology Letters* 6: 361–370.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2003.00442.x>
- Weiss M.R. 2006 Defecation behavior and ecology of insects. *Annual Review of Entomology* 51 (1): 635–661.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.49.061802.123212>
- Weiss M.R., Lind E.M., Jones M.T., Long J.D., Maupin J.L. 2003 Uniformity of leaf shelter construction by larvae of *Epargyreus clarus* (HesperIIDae), the silver-spotted skipper. *Journal of Insect Behavior* 16: 465–480.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1027399122333>
- Zacca T., Bravo F. 2012 Butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea and Hesperioidea) of the northern portion of the Chapada Diamantina, Bahia, Brazil. *Biota Neotropica* 12 (2): 117–126.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/S1676-06032012000200012>
- Zhang J., Cong Q., Shen J., Grishin N.V. 2022 Taxonomic changes suggested by the genomic analysis of HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera). *Insecta Mundi* 2022 (921): 1–135.
- Zhang J., Dolibaina D.R., Cong Q., Shen J., Song L., Mielke C.G.C., Casagrande M.M., Mielke O.H.H., Grishin N.V. 2023 Taxonomic notes on Neotropical HesperIIDae (Lepidoptera). *Zootaxa* 5271 (1): 91–114.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5271.1.3>